

D6.1(v1.0)

Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan

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WEBSITE	www.r-map.eu
COORDINATOR	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUP)
PROJECT OVERVIEW	R-Map aims to analyse the impact of remote working arrangements (RWAs) on the disparities between urban and rural regions in Europe. An Integrated Impact Assessment Framework (powered by the R-Map model) will be produced to assess the individual, social, economic, environmental and spatial impacts of RWAs. It will also allow decision-makers to monitor and assess how remote work arrangements affect people, communities, space, economy, and environment in urban and rural regions. Furthermore, R-Map will formulate policy recommendations on how to create environments conducive to remote work that are tailored to the needs of local governments in both urban and rural settings.

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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

Version Control Sheet

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v2.0	04/02/2025	Contributing Organisations & Reviewing partners Tables modified according to SC Decision	AUTH

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Contributing Organisations

Organisations
UT
UB
KU
SEERC
RIM
Q-PLAN
METREX
WR
ARX.NET
RWW
SURREY

Quality Reviewers

Organisations
All partners

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List of Abbreviations

Table 1: List of Abbreviations

AB	Advisory Board
AC	Associated Countries
AP	Associated Partner
APIs	Application Programming Interfaces
BEN	Beneficiaries
CA	Consortium Agreement
COO	Coordinator
DM	Dissemination Manager
DoA	Description of the Action
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer
QM	Quality Manager
RWAs	Remote Working Arrangements
SC	Steering Committee
TL	Task Leaders
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation
WPL	Work Package Leaders

Executive Summary

This report is the first version of a combined Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan (D6.1) for the EU-funded R-Map project. R-Map aims to explore how remote work affects the urban-rural divide in Europe by mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the impact of remote working arrangements (RWAs). It uses state-of-the-art research methods and works closely with relevant stakeholders to fully understand the impact of remote work and provide data-driven solutions. By integrating multiple data sources and advanced modelling techniques, the project aims to prepare for future trends.

The present document outlines the overall project management approach, quality assurance procedures, and data management principles. It details roles and responsibilities, work breakdown structures, progress reporting methods, financial management, payment schedules, risk management processes, and change control procedures. Additionally, it sets out best practices for handling data collected, created, or reused throughout the R-Map project, ensuring ethical and sound data management.

The present document represents the first of three planned versions of the combined R-Map Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan, submitted in M3. As a dynamic document, it will be updated on M15 and M36 to reflect the evolving data management needs of the project. This approach ensures an accurate, up-to-date, and comprehensive plan for managing R-Map's data throughout its lifecycle.

1. Introduction

This document constitutes the first version of the Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan of the project "R-Map - Mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the effects of RWAs in urban and rural areas", funded by the European Union Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon Europe under Grant Agreement (GA) No. 101132497.

The aim of R-Map is to analyse the impact of RWAs on the urban-rural divide in Europe. R-Map will develop an integrated impact assessment framework using the R-Map model to assess the individual, social, economic, environmental and spatial impacts of remote work. A visualisation platform will be created to enable decision-makers to monitor and evaluate how remote work affects people, communities, space, the economy and the environment in urban and rural areas. The tools will be applied at the local level in six representative use cases in the European Union (EU) and the Associated Countries (AC), including regions in Greece, the UK, Italy, Türkiye, the Netherlands-Germany and Austria-Switzerland. Using scenario building and forecasting methods, R-Map will explore the potential future impact of remote work in these regions over the next 5-10 years and provide policy recommendations on how to create an environment conducive to remote work, tailored to the needs of local governments in both urban and rural areas.

This initial Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan for the R-Map project focuses on four key goals:

- **Efficiency and Timeliness:** Making sure all project activities are completed on schedule and within budget.
- **Meeting Contract Standards:** Ensuring the project follows the high standards outlined in the agreement with the European Commission (EC).
- **Sound Data Management:** Explaining how data will be handled throughout the project, emphasizing its importance.
- **FAIR Data Principles:** Describing how the project will ensure collected data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) according to best practices.

With this in mind, the initial version of the Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan is organised into 13 separate chapters, as outlined below:

- **Chapter 2** provides an overview of the project, including information on the consortium, milestones, contractual deliverables and work plan.
- **Chapter 3** analyses the governance structure of the project and describes the roles and responsibilities of the partners in this respect.
- **Chapter 4** describes the management processes, focusing on document quality and formats, and conflict resolution procedures.
- **Chapter 5** focuses on the internal and external communication aspects of the project.
- **Chapter 6** describes the procedures for the distribution of payments made by the EC to the partners.
- **Chapter 7** provides information on reporting and risk management.
- **Chapter 8** explains the importance of the data collected or produced by R-Map and gives a detailed overview of the different data types and formats, data origins and expected volume. It concludes with

an overview of the usefulness of the data and a list of potential stakeholders who may find the data useful for re-use.

- **Chapter 9** describes the methods to be used to make research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable in the context of the R-Map project.
- **Chapter 10** is a brief outline of all the resources necessary for the FAIR project's data, as well as the responsibilities for data management.
- **Chapter 11** discusses other research outputs.
- **Chapter 12** discusses data security issues.
- **Chapter 13** provides information on the ethical aspects of data use.
- **Chapter 14** deals with other issues.
- **Chapter 15** concludes the document.
- **Annexed** in the document is an indicative template for the informed consent form.

The R-Map Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan is a dynamic document that will change and expand as the project progresses, with two updates planned over the course of the project (on M15 and M36). In addition, a continuous review is foreseen in relation to any significant changes during the lifespan of the project, such as new data, changes in consortium policy, external factors, etc.

2. Project overview

2.1 Consortium and work plan

The R-Map consortium brings together a balanced and multidisciplinary group of partners consisting of 12 complementary partners representing a total of 8 different countries (GR, NL, IT, TR, UK, AT, FR, BE) as presented below:

Table 2: R-Map consortium

Partner No	Role	Partner Name	Partner Short Name	Country
1	COO	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTh	Greece
2	BEN	UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE	UT	The Netherlands
3	BEN	UNIVERSITA COMMERCIALE LUIGI BOCCONI	UB	Italy
4	BEN	KOC UNIVERSITY	KU	Türkiye
5	BEN	KENTRO EREVNON NOTIOANATOLIKIS EVROPIS ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	SEERC	Greece
6	BEN	RESEARCH AND INNOVATION MANAGEMENT GMBH	RIM	Austria
7	BEN	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	Q-PLAN	Greece
8	BEN	LE RESEAU DES REGIONS ET DES AIRESMETROPOLITAINES D'EUROPE	METREX	France
9	BEN	WHITE RESEARCH SRL	WR	Belgium
10	BEN	ARX NET AE YPIRESIES KAI EPICHIRISIS DIADIKTYOU ANONIMI ETAIRIA	ARX.NET	Greece
11	BEN	MANDY LISA FRANZ	RWW	The Netherlands
12	AP	UNIVERSITY OF SURREY	SURREY	United Kingdom

The work plan of the project is presented in the following table:

Table 3: R-Map work plan

Activities per Work Package		Lead partner	Start month	End month
WP1	Setting the scene	KU	1	9
T1.1	Researching the current status of remote working arrangements in Europe and beyond	SEERC	1	5
T1.2	Understanding the potential spatial implications of remote working arrangements	AUTh	1	7
T1.3	Understanding the potential effects of remote working arrangements on the working and living conditions	KU	1	7
T1.4	Understanding the potential socio-economic effects of remote working arrangements	SURREY	1	7
T1.5	Large scale survey to capture perceptions, intentions and needs with regards to the changes brought about by remote working	RIM	1	9
WP2	Design of the R-Map model	UT	4	20
T2.1	Knowledge synthesis and co-design of the R-Map model	UT	4	12
T2.2	Definition and elaboration of the integrated analytical R-Map model including data harmonisation	UT	8	14
T2.3	Development of a typology of EU regions based on the R-Map model	SEERC	14	20
T2.4	Definition of a taxonomy of economic and social impacts of remote working	UB	14	20
WP3	Development of the R-Map visualization platform	ARX.NET	6	36
T3.1	Analysis of user requirements and design of the platform architecture	ARX.NET	6	12
T3.2	Collection and analysis of open data to be integrated in the R-Map visualisation platform	ARX.NET	8	36

Activities per Work Package		Lead partner	Start month	End month
T3.3	Development, integration and finetuning of the R-Map visualisation platform	ARX.NET	11	36
WP4	Anticipating and evaluating the impacts of remote working arrangements on different spaces	Q-PLAN	16	35
T4.1	Grounding the research in the 6 use case areas	Q-PLAN	16	23
T4.2	Forecasting and scenario development for assessing the impacts of remote working arrangements on the spatial, economic and social facets of the urban-rural divide	Q-PLAN	22	27
T4.3	Evaluating the impacts and trade-offs of remote working arrangements in the 6 use cases and co-creating policy measures	UB	27	31
T4.4	Cross-regional dialogues	WR	31	35
WP5	Dissemination, communication, exploitation and policy feedback	WR	1	36
T5.1	Dissemination and communication strategy, plan and activities	WR	1	36
T5.2	Innovation management and exploitation	RIM	1	36
T5.3	Clustering and cooperation with relevant projects, networks and initiatives	Q-PLAN	1	36
T5.4	Policy recommendations and replication guide	METREX	14	36
WP6	Project management and coordination	AUTh	1	36
T6.1	Coordination and quality management	AUTh	1	36
T6.2	Data management	AUTh	1	36
T6.3	Advisory Board set up and operation	WR	1	36
T6.4	Project meetings and reporting	AUTh	1	36

2.2 Project deliverables and milestones

The table below lists all project deliverables with the responsible partners and due dates.

Table 4: R-Map list of deliverables

WP	Deliverable No	Deliverable name	Lead partner	Due date (month)
1	D1.1	Current status and emerging trends of remote working arrangements in Europe and beyond	SEERC	5
1	D1.2	Spatial implications of remote working arrangements across Europe and beyond	AUTH	7
1	D1.3	Potential effects of remote working arrangements on the working and living conditions	KU	7
1	D1.4	Potential socio-economic effects of remote working arrangements	SURREY	7
2	D2.1 (v1.0)	The R-Map model	UT	12
2	D2.1 (v2.0)	The R-Map model	UT	14
2	D2.2	Typology of EU regions based on the effects of remote working on their urban-rural divide	SEERC	20
2	D2.3	Taxonomy of economic and social impacts of remote working arrangements	UB	20
3	D3.1 (v1.0)	The R-Map platform	ARX.NET	12
3	D3.1 (v2.0)	The R-Map platform	ARX.NET	16
3	D3.1 (v3.0)	The R-Map platform	ARX.NET	22
3	D3.1 (v4.0)	The R-Map platform	ARX.NET	36
4	D4.1	Use case areas' profiles	Q-PLAN	23
4	D4.2	Scenario building for assessing the impacts of remote working on the urban-rural divide	Q-PLAN	27
4	D4.3	Inclusive evaluation and co-creation of policy measures	UB	31

WP	Deliverable No	Deliverable name	Lead partner	Due date (month)
4	D4.4	Cross-regional dialogues	WR	35
5	D5.1 (v1.0)	Dissemination and Communication plan, activities and results	WR	3
5	D5.1 (v2.0)	Dissemination and Communication plan, activities and results	WR	15
5	D5.1 (v3.0)	Dissemination and Communication plan, activities and results	WR	36
5	D5.2 (v1.0)	Exploitation and Sustainability Plan	RIM	6
5	D5.2 (v2.0)	Exploitation and Sustainability Plan	RIM	18
5	D5.2 (v3.0)	Exploitation and Sustainability Plan	RIM	36
5	D5.3	R-Map replication guide and policy recommendations	METREX	36
5	D5.4 (v1.0)	R-Map policy briefs	AUTH	15
5	D5.4 (v2.0)	R-Map policy briefs	AUTH	36
6	D6.1 (v1.0)	Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan	AUTH	3
6	D6.1 (v2.0)	Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan	AUTH	15
6	D6.1 (v3.0)	Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan	AUTH	36

R-Map has 8 milestones throughout its lifetime, which are summarised below:

Table 5: Milestones of R-Map

WP	Milestone No	Milestone name	Lead partner	Due date (month)
6	1	Project kick-off meeting completed	AUTH	1
1	2	Large scale survey has been completed	RIM	9

WP	Milestone No	Milestone name	Lead partner	Due date (month)
2	3	R-Map model is operational	UT	14
3	4	First version of R-Map platform is launched	ARX.NET	20
5	5	Cluster meeting with sister projects implemented	Q-PLAN	26
4	6	6 policy workshops implemented	UB	31
3	7	Replication guide and policy recommendations ready for dissemination	METREX	36
5	8	Final plans for post project exploitation in motion	RIM	36

3. Project management and governance

3.1 Project management strategy

Project management includes all essential activities required to ensure the successful completion of the project within the technical and financial parameters set out in the GA and CA. WP6, led by AUTH, is responsible for overseeing the management and coordination of the project to ensure that it adheres to the agreed scope, budget, resources and quality standards. Any necessary changes or optimizations to achieve these goals will be discussed with the partners and decisions will be made upon their approval. Effective communication management practices are critical to ensure that relevant information is communicated to the appropriate parties and that timely decisions can be made efficiently. Quality management focuses on implementing control and assurance activities to maintain project quality and facilitate collaboration among consortium partners in delivering project results. Risk management is essential for assessing and mitigating potential project risks, emphasizing early identification and prevention.

3.2 Project management structure

The overall organizational structure of R-Map is shown in the following figure:

Figure 1: R-Map management structure

- **Steering Committee (SC):** It is made up of one person from each participating organisation. This group is responsible for making key decisions that guide the overall direction of the project. SC members have several responsibilities: ensuring that the project achieves its goals with high quality, keeping an eye on the budget and technical progress, and providing input for project reports.
- **Project Coordinator (PC):** Acts as an intermediary between the partners and the granting authority and oversees project decisions as head of the central decision-making committee. The PC is responsible for organising project tasks and managing all issues related to contracts with the EC and the technical and scientific activities of the consortium.
- **Quality Manager (QM):** Supports the SC and the PC in the implementation of the project. In particular, the main tasks of the QM are to draw up and monitor the implementation of the project management quality plan, to provide administrative and organisational support for project meetings and to ensure the effectiveness of internal communication.
- **Advisory Board (AB):** Leveraging their expertise, AB members address the present needs and challenges within their specific stakeholder communities, offering invaluable insights into our concepts, pilot initiatives, and project outcomes. Importantly, AB members foster connections with essential European and international stakeholders, advancing the broad acceptance and replication of R-MAP's findings
- **Exploitation Manager (EM):** Responsible for organising the R-Map activities and ensuring that the project results are effectively exploited. To achieve this, the EM develops the D5.2 "Exploitation and Sustainability Plan", which is elaborated by M6 and updated at least twice (at M18 and at project closure at M36).
- **Dissemination Manager (DM):** Responsible for developing and implementing a communication strategy. This involves the development of a plan (D5.1 "Dissemination and communication plan, activities and results"). This plan will be elaborated by M3 and updated at two key points during the project (M15 and M36).
- **Work Package Leaders (WPL):** Responsible for organising the partners involved in their specific Work Packages to ensure that the work done is of high quality, dealing with any administrative, technical or resource issues that arise within their Work Package on a day-to-day basis.
- **Task Leaders (TL):** Responsible for ensuring that the deliverables and results of their assigned tasks are completed in a timely manner. They work under the supervision of and report directly to the WPL.

4. Management processes and quality assurance

4.1 Document formats and naming conventions

Throughout the project, the PC and other partners will keep records in electronic or physical form. The PC will be responsible for overseeing the main project records, which include contracts, correspondence with the EC and project partners, deliverables, meeting minutes, progress reports and other important documents.

The WPL are responsible for sending the completed tasks of each Work Package to the PC. The PC has the sole responsibility for releasing the deliverables to the public or submitting them to the EC. Once a deliverable has been released it will be marked as version 1.0. The version number will only be updated if there are significant revisions or feedback from the EC, or if the deliverable is modified as described in the DoA attached to the GA. Only the PC is authorised to update the version number of a deliverable.

The table below shows the recommended formats and tools to use for electronic records (digital files).

Table 6: Recommended tools and formats for use in R-Map

Type	Format	Production Tool	Version
Documents	.docx	Microsoft Word	“Word 2010 or later”, Google Docs
Tabular and graphical data	.xlsx	Microsoft Excel	“Excel 2010 or later”, Google Docs
Presentations	.pptx	Microsoft PowerPoint	“PowerPoint 2010 or later”, Google Docs
Images	.jpeg, .png etc	Any software tool that can generate images	various
Compressed files	.zip	Any software tool that can produce .zip files	various

Partners are encouraged to use certain naming conventions when communicating and organising documents to facilitate the process. The recommended convention is to use titles and versions that are clear and descriptive. The general file naming conventions to be used are as follows:

[Name of project]_[Name of the document]_[Version]_[Partner acronym]_[Date].[Extension]

where:

- **Name of project:** R-Map
- **Name of the document:** The unique title of the document. Specifically, for deliverables, the deliverable number and official name as listed in the GA should be part of the document name
- **Version:** The versioning number of the document
- **Partner acronym:** The partner acronym should be used as defined in the GA

- **Date:** The date on which the latest version of the document was modified, in the form of “YYYY_MM_DD”
- **Extension:** is the file extension (e.g. pdf., doc., etc.)

An example document name that follows the recommended format is as follows:

“R-Map_D6.1Management&QualityPlan&DataManagementPlan_v1.0_AUTh_20240430.pdf”

4.2 Quality assurance processes of deliverables

Before approval and release, all deliverables produced within R-Map will be subject to a thorough quality control process. The deliverables must successfully pass this process before they can be officially released. Throughout this process, each deliverable is evaluated to ensure that the document is coherent, does not contradict or overlap with other different deliverables, is relevant to the topic and meets the project objectives, is well structured according to the deliverable template and contains appropriate language elements.

The initial quality review is performed by the partner responsible for creating the deliverable. Following this review, the deliverable is then reviewed by two partners, acting as quality reviewers who provide feedback on any issues using a quality review form that has been distributed to all partners. The only exception is **Deliverable 6.1: Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan**, which will be thoroughly reviewed by all consortium partners prior to submission to ensure that everyone is aware of and agrees with the project management processes. If any problems or deficiencies are found in the deliverable, it will be rejected and returned to the partner for any necessary improvements.

The reviewers are expected to complete their assessment within **5 working days** and provide feedback to the partner, who will then have **3 days** to address the issues and resubmit the deliverable for further review. This process continues until all issues have been resolved. Once the deliverable has been approved by the quality reviewers, it is sent to the PC for final evaluation. The quality reviewers are selected based on their individual expertise and assigned effort on the project and are listed in the following table:

Table 7: R-Map deliverable reviewers

WP	Deliverable No	Deliverable name	Lead partner	Reviewers
1	D1.1	Current status and emerging trends of remote working arrangements in Europe and beyond	SEERC	KU, AUTh
1	D1.2	Spatial implications of remote working arrangements across Europe and beyond	AUTh	UT, UB
1	D1.3	Potential effects of remote working arrangements on the working and living conditions	KU	SEERC, SURREY
1	D1.4	Potential socio-economic effects of remote working arrangements	SURREY	KU, Q-PLAN

2	D2.1 (v1.0)	The R-Map model	UT	ARX.NET, AUTH
2	D2.1 (v2.0)	The R-Map model	UT	ARX.NET, AUTH
2	D2.2	Typology of EU regions based on the effects of remote working on their urban-rural divide	SEERC	SURREY, AUTH
2	D2.3	Taxonomy of economic and social impacts of remote working arrangements	UB	SEERC, UT
3	D3.1 (v1.0)	The R-Map platform	ARX.NET	UT, UB
3	D3.1 (v2.0)	The R-Map platform	ARX.NET	UT, UB
3	D3.1 (v3.0)	The R-Map platform	ARX.NET	UT, UB
3	D3.1 (v4.0)	The R-Map platform	ARX.NET	UT, UB
4	D4.1	Use case areas' profiles	Q-PLAN	RIM, WR
4	D4.2	Scenario building for assessing the impacts of remote working on the urban-rural divide	Q-PLAN	AUTH, KU
4	D4.3	Inclusive evaluation and co-creation of policy measures	UB	Q-PLAN, RWW
4	D4.4	Cross-regional dialogues	WR	Q-PLAN, METREX
5	D5.1 (v1.0)	Dissemination and Communication plan, activities and results	WR	UB, RIM
5	D5.1 (v2.0)	Dissemination and Communication plan, activities and results	WR	UB, RIM
5	D5.1 (v3.0)	Dissemination and Communication plan, activities and results	WR	UB, RIM
5	D5.2 (v1.0)	Exploitation and Sustainability Plan	RIM	WR, SURREY
5	D5.2 (v2.0)	Exploitation and Sustainability Plan	RIM	WR, SURREY
5	D5.2 (v3.0)	Exploitation and Sustainability Plan	RIM	WR, SURREY

5	D5.3	R-Map replication guide and policy recommendations	METREX	WR, ARX.NET
5	D5.4 (v1.0)	R-Map policy briefs	AUTH	METREX, RWW
5	D5.4 (v2.0)	R-Map policy briefs	AUTH	METREX, RWW
6	D6.1 (v1.0)	Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan	AUTH	ALL
6	D6.1 (v2.0)	Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan	AUTH	ALL
6	D6.1 (v3.0)	Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan	AUTH	ALL

4.3 Conflict resolution

Project and quality management activities, along with partners' understanding of their responsibilities, will ensure effective implementation of the project plan and achievement of its goals. Decisions are made by the responsible partners based on the roles outlined in the GA and CA. Maintaining transparency and open communication among team members is critical to anticipating challenges and conflicts.

Throughout the project, partners may encounter issues that require resolution and agreement. TL and WPL should immediately inform the PC of any conflicts that arise so that temporary solutions can be proposed. The PC has ultimate responsibility for conflict resolution, with an emphasis on resolving issues at the lowest level possible, starting at the task level, and using negotiation skills. If the efforts of the PC to mediate the conflict are unsuccessful, the PC will refer the conflict to the SC for a final decision. The SC will attempt to address changes or resolve conflicts by reaching agreement between the parties. If agreement cannot be reached and conflicts persist, the SC will make a decision by vote. The project's CA will provide more information on decision-making, conflict resolution and the management of internal administrative and financial matters. However, the final say on mediation and decisions rests with the PC and the SC. If necessary, the PC will inform the EC and ask for feedback.

5. Communication processes

5.1 Internal communication

Communication between the PC and project partners takes place through various available channels such as email, telephone, teleconferences and meetings. Internal communication can be categorised into formal and informal communication, with the PC being primarily responsible for ensuring efficient and effective communication within the team. It is necessary to document important communications on issues such as sending deliverables and scheduling meetings, as well as any formal communications such as project meetings, by taking minutes and maintaining a written record, either electronically or on paper. Informal communication takes place between the PC, the WPL and the partners through methods such as telephone calls and informal emails and may not have written documentation. The PC and the WPL should communicate with the project partners on a regular basis in order to closely monitor project progress and all Work Packages, and to promptly address any issues that may arise.

The R-Map project has scheduled 7 project meetings, where more information can be found in Part A of the DoA on page 15. The PC is responsible for taking minutes of all project meetings, which are then circulated to all partners for approval.

5.2 External communication

The partners involved in the project are encouraged to communicate with external parties such as companies, authorities and other relevant bodies. The consortium will create its own website for external communication and will interact with external stakeholders via email, social media accounts and social platforms. When communicating externally, partners should always mention details related to the project, such as the project acronym, the EU programme and the GA number.

The PC is the main point of contact for the project when communicating with the Project Officer (PO) of the EC. He is responsible for updating the project portal with communication activities, milestones, deliverables and progress reports. The PC also provides information requested by PO and communicates any information from the EC to the partners. **Partners should not communicate directly with the PO** and should only do so in rare circumstances with the PO's permission. The PC will keep the partners informed of all important communications with the EC.

6. Payments

Payments shall be made in euro to the bank account indicated by the coordinator and shall be distributed to the partners without undue delay after receipt of the payments from the granting authority and in accordance with the provisions of the GA.

The EC will make three separate payments of the EU contribution over the project's lifetime.

1. At the start of the project, 80% of the EU funding will be provided as pre-financing upon signature of the GA, with the Grantor Authority retaining 5% of the maximum grant amount for the Mutual Insurance Mechanism. Pre-financing will be distributed to the partners no later than thirty (30) calendar days after payment by the Granting Authority.

2. Interim payment after the end of the 1st project period. The interim payment will be made within 90 days of receipt of the periodic report.

3. Final payment after the end of the 2nd project period – end of the project. The final payment will be made within 90 days of receipt of the periodic report.

7. Monitoring and Risk management

7.1 Internal and external reporting

Every six months, a concise progress report will be meticulously prepared by each project partner and the WPL to succinctly outline the progress made, including achievements against objectives, and the costs incurred during the reporting period. Following the submission of individual semester progress reports, the PC will compile a comprehensive "**Internal Semester Report**" encompassing the entirety of the project. All individual Semester Progress Reports are expected to be submitted to the PC no later than 15 days after the conclusion of the respective reporting period. The PC will then provide feedback within 15 days of receipt. Failure to provide feedback within this designated timeframe will be interpreted as acceptance of the submitted report.

Regarding the external reporting, the PC has overall responsibility for the preparation and timely submission of project reports to the EC. All partners contribute to the preparation of the reports. In R-Map, two such reports are required at the end of each of the two reporting periods (M1 to M18 and M19 to M36). The exact content of these reports is specified in the GA (Article 21, p. 38 - 40).

7.2 Risk management plan

Risk management involves the identification, analysis, monitoring and control of potential risks that may affect the project's delivery. It is an ongoing process implemented throughout the project's life. Risks are mitigated and controlled through the use of established project planning and control methodologies, and the division of project work into Work Packages also helps to minimise internal risks.

Risks are identified and analysed throughout the project and each partner is responsible for communicating any potential risks to the PC and for identifying any additional risks that may arise during the project. Two categories of risks have been identified:

- **Internal risks**, which relate to the dynamics within the project team (made up of numerous experts with different backgrounds and geographically dispersed), potential delays, team changes, etc.
- **External risks**, which come from the project's stakeholders, but can also result from an inappropriate project strategy or poor execution.

Potential risks that could significantly affect the project's progress and outcome have been identified and evaluated against their impact and probability, and appropriate contingency plans have been developed. The list of risks will be reviewed and updated regularly, either as required or every six months. The project's main internal and external risks and contingency plans, as identified in the GA, are summarised in the following table.

Table 8: Risks and contingency plans

Description of risk	Linked WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Low response rate of the survey (Low probability/high impact)	1	We will use Prolific as the main survey recruitment tool. Prolific outperforms other platforms regarding data quality, transparency, ethics and attrition rates. RIM has extensive experience (including training for data security and ethics) with the managing of global, large-scale surveys.
Incomplete coverage/uncertainties in social, economic and spatial data at the European scale at NUTS2/3 level (medium probability/high impact)	2	In such case, we will implement the R-Map model at the country scale, with the drawback that regional differences will not be visible taken into account. Alternatively, we can use data from regions with similar characteristics for which data is available.
Difficulties in identifying and forecasting the driving forces of change and developing relevant scenarios (Low probability/high impact)	3	For each use case, we will liaise with local key actors (some Letters of Support have already been provided) and perform regional surveys to get the local's perspective on the phenomenon. The scenario building methods will be adapted to the cases particularities.
Changes in project team (Medium probability/low impact)	4	Partners are required to include substitutes with equivalent qualifications and experience and inform them in detail on R-Map.
Delays in the project timetable (Low probability/medium impact)	6	The Steering Committee applies tailored mitigation plans (i) reallocation of resources, (ii) parallel task execution, (iii) rescheduling.
Delays in the process of the U.K. associating to Horizon Europe (Medium probability/low impact)	6	There is a risk of the U.K. partner not securing funding or not meeting the EC deadlines due to the different timeframes of UK internal procedures. According to the current commitments and arrangements of the UK Government, all successful Horizon Europe proposals are funded through a separate process supported by UKRI. Any timeframe risk will be mitigated based on the relevant experience of SURREY with EC and UKRI funded projects. All partners will be kept informed by SURREY about actions, if this risk arises. For the extreme event that SURREY will not be granted funding through these routes, the CA will contain contingency provisions to assign its activities to another partner of equivalent expertise and capabilities.

8. Data summary

8.1 Purpose of data collection or generation and its relation to the objectives of the project

R-Map involves the collection or production of meaningful, non-sensitive data and research findings that are necessary to generate insights to support the project's activities and achieve evidence-based results. This data, which may be quantitative, qualitative or a combination of both, will be analysed using a variety of methodological approaches to inform R-Map's activities, deliver evidence-based results and achieve the project's objectives. Many activities were planned to achieve these objectives. These activities will involve the collection, processing and production of different types of data to support evidence-based outcomes and add value to the project. The main R-Map activities that will collect, process or produce data are as follows:

- Analysis of the current RWAs, as well as their spatial implications, effects in living and working conditions and socio-economic effects.
- Collection of perceptions, intentions and needs regarding remote working.
- Co-design and elaboration of the R-Map model, development of an EU regions typology and a taxonomy of impacts.
- Development of the R-Map visualization platform.
- Diagnosis of 6 use case areas, forecasting and scenario development for assessing the impacts of RWAs on the urban-rural divide.
- Evaluating the impacts of RWAs, co-creating policy measures and organising cross-regional dialogues.
- Elaboration of Policy recommendations.
- Dissemination, communication, stakeholder engagement and networking.
- Advisory Board set up and operation.

The following tables provide a list of the main data sets to be collected/generated during the project activities.

WP1 - Setting the scene

Name of Dataset	Data on current RWAs	Code: 01	
Relevant activity	Analysis of the current RWAs, as well as their spatial implications, effects in living and working conditions and socio-economic effects		
Data elements	Personal data: name and surname, gender, organisation, familial status, position, email, brief description of professional profile, years of engagement in remote work		
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf)		

Data collection/generation process	Conducting personal online interviews with policy makers and business decision makers to capture the views of the tripartite governance-employer-employee. Conducting a survey or poll to collect the views of remote workers.
Data Availability	Open <input type="checkbox"/> Closed <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure
Data storage	SEERC repository, RWW repository

Name of Dataset	Data on spatial implications	Code: 02	
Relevant activity	Analysis of the current RWAs, as well as their spatial implications, effects in living and working conditions and socio-economic effects		
Data elements	Personal data: name and surname, gender, organisation, position, email, brief description of professional profile.		
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf)		
Data collection/generation process	Conducting personal online interviews with key local stakeholders to gain a deeper understanding of local spatial changes due to remote work.		
Data Availability	Open <input type="checkbox"/> Closed <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure		
Data storage	AUPh repository		

Name of Dataset	Data on working and living conditions	Code: 03	
Relevant activity	Analysis of the current RWAs, as well as their spatial implications, effects on living and working conditions and socio-economic effects		
Data elements	Online publications, reports, and an remote work-related dataset.		

Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf)		
Data collection/generation process	Through desk research		
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Closed <input type="checkbox"/>	
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure		
Data storage	KU repository		

Name of Dataset	Data on socio-economic effects	Code: 04	
Relevant activity	Analysis of the current RWAs, as well as their spatial implications, effects in living and working conditions and socio-economic effects		
Data elements	Personal data: name and surname, gender, organisation, position, email, brief description of professional profile		
Data type	Qualitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf)		
Data collection/generation process	Conducting personal interviews with key stakeholders to gain a deeper understanding of socio-economic changes due to remote work.		
Data Availability	Open <input type="checkbox"/>	Closed <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure		
Data storage	SURREY repository		

Name of Dataset	Survey data	Code: 05	
Relevant activity	Collection of perceptions, intentions and needs regarding remote working		
Data elements	Information regarding: gender, age in years, years spent in education, average number of hours worked per week for payment, average number of hours worked per week		

	<p>without payment, and average number of hours worked per week remotely.</p> <p>The survey covers various aspects related to remote work, including geo-located data on past, current, and future working and living conditions, as well as concerns such as extra costs, job security, productivity, career advancement, health and safety risks, family and care arrangements, and overall well-being.</p>		
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf)		
Data collection/generation process	<p>Online data collection by conducting a survey using Prolific and LimeSurvey to target ≥20,000 participants. All data collected will be anonymised.</p> <p>Participation in the survey is voluntary and participants have the right to refuse or discontinue participation at any time. Completion of the survey is required to receive payment and incomplete data will not be included in the analysis.</p> <p>There are no foreseeable risks associated with taking part in the survey. By completing the questionnaire, participants give their consent for the data to be used for research purposes and for the results to be disseminated through various channels, while maintaining anonymity.</p>		
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Closed <input type="checkbox"/>	
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure		
Data storage	RIM repository		
Any other comments	Data will be openly shared via the Open Science Framework (OSF) after the main publication has been accepted.		

WP2: Design of the R-Map model

Name of Dataset	R-Map model data	Code: 06
Relevant activity	Co-design and elaboration of the R-Map model, development of an EU regions typology and a taxonomy of impacts.	

Data elements	Textual data collected through technical workshops and from reports, spatial and statistical data/maps sourced from publicly accessible data repositories, and data sourced from the internet through Application Programming Interfaces (APIs).		
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx)/(.csv), document (.docx/.pdf/.txt), spatial data (shapefiles /.shp/GeoJSON/xarray/.tif), audio recording (.mp3, .wav).		
Data collection/generation process	Through a series of technical workshops between the experts of the consortium partners and identified external experts, through sourcing and processing secondary data (spatial / statistical with spatial reference) that are publicly available/accessible, and sourcing and processing data from the internet through APIs, e.g. social media data.		
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Closed <input type="checkbox"/>
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure		
Data storage	UT repository		
Any other comments	<p>Data will be open anonymised after careful examination that there are not serious ethical concerns.</p> <p>For UT the retention time is 10 years, according to the Dutch code of Research Integrity.</p>		

Name of Dataset	Data on typology of EU regions	Code: 07	
Relevant activity	Co-design and elaboration of the R-Map model, development of an EU regions typology and a taxonomy of impacts		
Data elements	Data and maps at EU level (NUTS 1/NUTS 2/ NUTS 3)		
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx, .csv), document (.docx/.pdf/.txt), spatial files (shapefile .shp), (GeoJSON), (.tif)		

Data collection/generation process	By using previous knowledge and data from Task 2.2
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Closed <input type="checkbox"/>
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure
Data storage	Partners' repositories
Any other comments	For UT the retention time is 10 years, according to the Dutch code of Research Integrity

Name of Dataset	Data on the taxonomy of remote work effects	Code: 08
Relevant activity	Co-design and elaboration of the R-Map model, development of an EU regions typology and a taxonomy of impacts	
Data elements	Textual data collected through desk research	
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/> Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx/.csv), document (.docx/.pdf/.txt)	
Data collection/generation process	By using previous knowledge from WP1 and WP2 and results from literature research	
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Closed <input type="checkbox"/>
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure	
Data storage	Partners' repositories	

WP3: Development of the R-Map visualization platform

Name of Dataset	R-Map platform data	Code: 09
Relevant activity	Development of the R-Map visualization platform	
Data elements	Machine generated data, images, shapefiles, infographics collected through workshops and documentation	
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/> Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), images (.jpeg), shapefiles (.shp)
Data collection/generation process	Through extensive desk research, a technical and a digital workshop, collecting, storing and combining existing surveys, and using our EU survey results (20000 responses) of Task 1.5 and Task 2.2 and Task 2.3.
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Closed <input type="checkbox"/>
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure
Data storage	R-Map platform

WP4: Anticipating and evaluating the impacts of remote working arrangements on different spaces

Name of Dataset	Use cases data	Code: 10
Relevant activity	Diagnosis of 6 use case areas, forecasting and scenario development for assessing the impacts of RWAs on the urban-rural divide.	
Data elements	<p>Personal data: name and surname, gender, organisation, position, email, brief description of professional profile.</p> <p>Information regarding: experts' views on housing land use and economic conditions, etc., as well as citizens' views, problems, needs and future plans regarding remote work.</p>	
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/> Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx, .csv), document (.docx/.pdf), shapefiles (.shp), images (.png, .tif)	
Data collection/generation process	By interviewing experts and conducting 6 regional surveys of 1000 people each	
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Closed <input type="checkbox"/>	
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure	
Data storage	Partners' repositories	
Any other comments	<p>Anonymised and aggregated data will be included in the public deliverable. Personal data will remain confidential.</p> <p>For UT the retention time is 10 years, according to the Dutch code of Research Integrity.</p>	

Name of Dataset	Forecasting and scenario building data	Code: 11	
Relevant activity	Diagnosis of 6 use case areas, forecasting and scenario development for assessing the impacts of RWAs on the urban-rural divide.		
Data elements	Textual data collected using the Delphi method maps		
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf)		
Data collection/generation process	Using the Delphi method with 5-10 stakeholders in each region		
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Closed <input type="checkbox"/>	
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure		
Data storage	Partners' repositories		

Name of Dataset	Data on the evaluation and co-creation of policy measures	Code: 12	
Relevant activity	Evaluating the impacts of RWAs, co-creating policy measures and organising cross-regional dialogues		
Data elements	Textual and spatial data collected through workshops and webinars		
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf), spatial data (shapefiles - .shp / GeoJSON)		
Data collection/generation process	By conducting 6 policy workshops and internal webinars		
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Closed <input type="checkbox"/>	
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure		

Data storage	Partners' repositories
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Name of Dataset	Cross-regional dialogues data	Code: 13	
Relevant activity	Evaluating the impacts of RWAs, co-creating policy measures and organising cross-regional dialogues		
Data elements	Textual data collected through the cross-regional dialogues		
Data type	Qualitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input type="checkbox"/>
Format	document (.docx/.pdf) and/or spreadsheet file (.xlsx)		
Data collection/generation process	By organising 6 online cross-regional dialogues, using various interactive platforms, (to be decided later) among the participating regions as well as with regions outside the consortium. Each cross regional dialogue will focus on the results of 1 use case only. The scope of the dialogues is to present the scenarios and discuss their impacts, while exchanging knowledge and experience through interactive discussions, building trust and enhancing openness, transparency and engagement (i.e. RRI principles).		
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Closed <input type="checkbox"/>	
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure		
Data storage	Project repository		

WP5: Dissemination, communication, exploitation and policy feedback

Name of Dataset	Policy recommendations data	Code: 14	
Relevant activity	Elaboration of Policy recommendations		
Data elements	Guides and briefs collected by the Policy Roundtable		
Data type	Qualitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf)		
Data collection/generation process	Through the organization of the Policy Roundtable and the accumulation of lessons learned throughout the implementation of the project.		

Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Closed <input type="checkbox"/>
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure
Data storage	Partners' repositories

Name of Dataset	Social media, website and newsletter statistics	Code: 15
Relevant activity	Dissemination, communication, stakeholder engagement and networking	
Data elements	Number of followers (related social media accounts), number of unique visits (website), number of newsletters released, number of newsletter subscribers, number of video views (2 promotional videos). Additional metrics may be considered, in line with the project's Dissemination and Communication Plan.	
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/> Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf)	
Data collection/generation process	Through: (i) the statistics tool offered by the social media platforms, (ii) google analytics used on the website, (iii) mailchimp statistics tool for the newsletter.	
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Closed <input type="checkbox"/>	
Data storage	Project repository	

Name of Dataset	Data from dissemination events and activities	Code: 16
Relevant activity	Dissemination, communication, stakeholder engagement and networking	
Data elements	Number of external events/conferences attended, number of participants to final dissemination event, information about the content of the event, information about participants.	
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/> Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf), photos (.jpg, .png).	

Data collection/generation process	Through the participation of the project partners in relevant external events and the organisation of the Final dissemination event.
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Closed <input type="checkbox"/>
Data storage	Project repository

Name of Dataset	Data from clustering activities	Code: 17	
Relevant activity	Dissemination, communication, stakeholder engagement and networking		
Data elements	(i) data on collaborative actions with relevant projects, networks and initiatives, (ii) data and information about attending external project events.		
Data type	Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf)		
Data collection/generation process	Through several actions to be organised among R-Map and relevant projects, networks and initiatives, as well as the participation of R-Map partners in events outside the project.		
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Closed <input type="checkbox"/>		
Data storage	Partner's repositories		

WP6: Project management and coordination

Name of Dataset	Advisory Board Data	Code: 18	
Relevant activity	Advisory Board set up and operation		
Data elements	Personal data: name and surname, gender, organisation,, position, type of stakeholder, email, online profile (e.g. LinkedIn), area of expertise, city/country, networks and connections.		
Data type	Qualitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/>	Both <input type="checkbox"/>
Format	spreadsheet file (.xlsx), document (.docx/.pdf)		

Data collection/generation process	Each partner must identify at least 5 appropriate stakeholders from their network and provide the consortium with access to publicly available information about them. These individuals will be assessed through a ranking mechanism and, the most suitable ones will be selected to be formally invited to join the AB as members.
Data Availability	Open <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Closed <input type="checkbox"/>
Retention time	Up to 5 years after Project's closure
Data storage	Project repository

8.2 Origin of data and re-use of pre-existing data

Within the R-Map activities, it is expected that new data will be collected and generated and existing data will be used. The new data will mainly be generated by the research and co-design activities of the project and will be shared with the consortium partners by the stakeholders involved in these activities. Existing data used during the project will mainly consist of data collected through literature reviews and desk research, publicly accessible spatial and statistical data and data sourced from the internet through APIs.

Table 9: Origin of data

Name of dataset	Dataset code	Origin
Data on current RWAs	1	Policymakers and business decision-makers
Data on spatial implications	2	Policymakers, urban planners, real estate agents, co-working space owners
Data on working and living conditions	3	R-Map partners
Data on socioeconomic effects	4	Local authorities, decision-makers, Civil Society Organisations
Survey data	5	Remote and non-remote workers
R-Map model data	6	R-Map partners and external experts
Data on typology of EU regions	7	R-Map partners
Data on the taxonomy of remote work effects	8	R-Map partners

R-Map platform data	9	R-Map partners
Use cases data	10	Experts (Real estate agents, municipal authorities, etc.) and citizens (remote and non-remote workers)
Forecasting and scenario building data	11	R-Map partners and stakeholders
Data on the evaluation and co-creation of policy measures	12	R-Map partners and stakeholders
Cross-regional dialogues data	13	R-Map partners and stakeholders
Policy recommendations data	14	R-Map partners and stakeholders
Social media, website and newsletter statistics	15	R-Map stakeholders and general public
Data from dissemination events and activities	16	R-Map stakeholders and general public
Data from clustering activities	17	R-Map stakeholders, Stakeholders from Relevant initiatives
Advisory Board Data	18	R-Map partners and AB members

8.3 Expected size of data

Table 10: Expected size of data

Name of dataset	Dataset code	Expected size
Data on current RWAs	1	More than 25 MB
Data on spatial implications	2	More than 25 MB
Data on working and living conditions	3	More than 25 MB
Data on socio-economic effects	4	More than 25 MB
Survey data	5	More than 100 MB

R-Map model data	6	More than 1 GB
Data on typology of EU regions	7	More than 15 MB
Data on the taxonomy of remote work effects	8	More than 15 MB
R-Map platform data	9	More than 1 GB
Use cases data	10	Less than 15 MB
Forecasting and scenario building data	11	Less than 15 MB
Data on the evaluation and co-creation of policy measures	12	Less than 15 MB
Cross-regional dialogues data	13	Less than 15 MB
Policy recommendations data	14	More than 50 MB
Social media, website and newsletter statistics	15	Less than 1 GB
Data from dissemination events and activities	16	Up to 5 GB
Data from clustering activities	17	Up to 1 GB
Advisory Board Data	18	Less than 20 MB

8.4 Data utility

Table 11: Data utility

Name of dataset	Dataset code	Stakeholder group	Utility
Data on current RWAs	1	Project partners	Contribute to the design of the R-Map model and other project deliverables, research publications, and materials
Data on spatial implications	2	Project partners	Contribute to the design of the R-Map model and other project deliverables, research publications, and materials

Data on working and living conditions	3	Project partners	Contribute to the design of the R-Map model and other project deliverables, research publications, and materials
Data on socio-economic effects	4	Project partners	Contribute to the design of the R-Map model and other project deliverables, research publications, and materials
Survey data	5	Project partners	Contribute to the design of the R-Map model and other project deliverables, research publications, and materials
R-Map model data	6	Project partners	Contribute to the design of the R-Map model
Data on typology of EU regions	7	Project partners	Contribute to the design of the R-Map model
Data on the taxonomy of remote work effects	8	Project partners	Contribute to the design of the R-Map model
R-Map platform data	9	Project partners	Contribute to the development of the R-Map platform
Use cases data	10	Project partners	Contribute to the grounding of research in 6 use case areas
Forecasting and scenario building data	11	Project partners	Contribute to assessing the impacts of RWAs
Data on the evaluation and co-creation of policy measures	12	Project partners Policy makers at regional, national and EU level	Contribute to the evaluation of the R-Map project
Cross-regional dialogues data	13	Project partners Policy makers at regional, national and EU level METREX network	Contribute to the evaluation of the R-Map project

Policy recommendations data	14	Project partners Policy makers at regional, national and EU level R-Map network	Contribute to research publications and materials
Social media, website and newsletter statistics	15	Project partners	Monitoring of the progress and impact of the dissemination and communication strategy of the project
Data from dissemination events and activities	16	R-Map stakeholders	Monitoring of the progress and impact of the dissemination and communication strategy of the project
Data from clustering activities	17	R-Map stakeholders Stakeholders of relevant initiatives	Monitoring of the progress of the clustering efforts of the project
Advisory Board Data	18	Project partners	Contribute to the establishment and effective operation of the R-Map Advisory Board (AB)

9. Fair data

While quality of data management is not an objective in itself, one of the challenges facing the research community is the need to discover, access and re-use high-quality data sets. The guidelines¹ issued by the EC for data management plans stress the significance of ensuring that data from Horizon Europe projects is easily Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) to guarantee effective management. This involves utilizing standards and metadata to enhance data discoverability, outlining data sharing processes and identifying which data will be open, enabling data exchange through open repositories, and promoting data reuse.

The FAIR principles as described by the GO FAIR Initiative² are:

Findable

- The first step in (re)using data is finding it. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Machine-readable metadata is essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, so this is an essential part of the FAIRification process.

Accessible

- Once the user finds the required data, she/he/they need to know how they can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorisation.

Interoperable

- The data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.

Reusable

- The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

² <https://www.go-fair.org/go-fair-initiative/>

9.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All data generated by the R-Map project will be discoverable with associated metadata. The metadata for each dataset will consist of descriptive elements such as title, abstract, author, and search terms, as well as administrative details such as creation and modification dates, and file type. The R-Map research data will be stored in the Zenodo repository, which has been chosen for specific reasons.

- Zenodo is part of OpenAIRE, a program dedicated to enabling open access to research in Europe. It serves as a digital repository for researchers who do not have access to institutional or thematic repositories for storing their publications and data.
- Since its inception, Zenodo has become a well-regarded research data repository, mentioned in the Horizon 2020 FAIR data management guidelines and included in the OpenAIRE recommendation list for finding a suitable research data repository.
- Zenodo provides long-term bit-level data preservation and adheres to the Open Archival Information System reference model. In addition, Zenodo adheres to the FAIR Data Principles.
- Zenodo provides automated DOI versioning for all submissions and allows up to 50GB of data per submission, with the ability to upload multiple submissions. The platform accepts multiple file formats, including publications, posters, presentations, datasets, images, software, and video/audio content.

Using a consistent naming structure for project data files can improve their visibility and discoverability. R-Map ensures that file names are standardis

ed to indicate content, status, and version, making them easier to organize and find. This makes it easier for project staff and stakeholders to quickly locate, categorize, and manage files.

The UK Data Archive suggests that it is best practice to create concise and descriptive names for data files to make them easy to classify. It is recommended that you avoid using spaces, periods, or special characters, and instead use underscores to separate elements in the file name. In addition, including versioning in the naming convention helps to clearly indicate any changes or edits made to a file. With this in mind, data is uploaded using the following naming convention:

[Name of project]_[Number of Work Package]_[Name of dataset]_[Version]_[Date].[Extension]

where:

- **Name of project:** R-Map
- **Number of Work Package:** The number of Work Package where the data was collected/generated
- **Name of dataset:** A short version of the title of the dataset
- **Version:** The versioning number of a dataset
- **Date:** The date on which the latest version of the dataset was modified, in the form of “YYYY_MM_DD”
- **Extension:** is the file extension (e.g. pdf., doc., etc.)

An example of a dataset name following the suggested scheme would be:

“R-Map_WP1_SurveyData_v1.0_20241031.pdf”

9.2 Making data accessible

To ensure that R-Map has a significant impact, the project will promote the sharing of results and deliverables within and beyond the consortium. Project data that could be useful to external parties will be made available, while protecting the confidentiality and privacy of the stakeholders who provided the data. Any personal data will be anonymised before being released to the public, in accordance with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). OpenAIRE's Amnesia tool will be used where necessary to ensure anonymisation of data. All personal data collected or generated will be considered as closed data until it is anonymised.

R-Map's open data will be easily accessible through a standard web browser on a computer, smartphone or tablet, without the need for specialised methods, software or documentation. Users can easily navigate to the Zenodo website using popular browsers such as Mozilla, Google Chrome, Internet Explorer or Safari. By entering the name of the R-Map project or related keywords into Zenodo's search engine, users can easily find the project's open data for re-use. Access to restricted data is restricted to project partners only.

9.3 Making data interoperable

In R-Map, data interoperability is considered essential to improve the usability of data, to extend its accessibility to a wider audience, and to foster collaboration to generate new knowledge. R-Map has adopted in its data management methodology the use of metadata vocabularies, standards and methods to enhance the interoperability of the data collected/generated through its activities.

The Dublin Core metadata standard enables the sharing of private data by providing a concise set of metadata elements that promote data quality and consistency. These elements, such as title, creator and author, are clearly defined in natural language and can be easily converted to machine-readable formats such as XML and HTML for efficient machine processing. The standard allows for optional and repeatable elements, with options for refinement through the use of encoding and vocabulary schemes, ensuring compatibility with other data sources in a linked data environment. The following table presents the vocabulary of the Dublin Core Metadata standard³.

Table 12: Dublin Core Metadata standard vocabulary

No	Element	Element definition
1	Title	A name given to the resource
2	Creator	An entity primarily responsible for making the content of the resource
3	Subject	The topic of the content of the resource
4	Description	An account of the content of the resource

³ Sugimoto, S., Baker, T., & Weibel, S. L. (2002). Dublin Core: Process and Principles. Lecture Notes in Computer Science Digital Libraries: People, Knowledge, and Technology, 25-35.

No	Element	Element definition
5	Publisher	An entity responsible for making the resource available
6	Contributor	An entity responsible for making contributions to the content of the resource
7	Date	A date associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource
8	Type	The nature or genre of the content of the resource
9	Format	The physical or digital manifestation of the resource
10	Identifier	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.
11	Source	A reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived
12	Language	A language of the intellectual content of the resource
13	Relation	A reference to a related resource
14	Coverage	The extent or scope of the content of the resource
15	Rights	Information about rights held in and over the resource

Zenodo enables compatibility of publicly available data by storing its metadata in JSON format with a specified schema. This includes the inclusion of HTML microdata, which allows machine-readable data to be inserted into HTML documents in structured name-value pairs. In addition, the JSON schema provides a set of standard vocabularies in microdata format that can be applied to markup pages for improved visibility in major search engines.

9.4 Increase data re-use

R-Map will use the Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0 (CC-BY-NC 4.0)⁴ license for the data produced by the project. This license allows the work to be shared and modified as long as the creator is credited and any derivative works are shared under a similar license. This type of license is commonly used and recommended by many open research data projects and stakeholders.

⁴ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/>

All open data collected will be made available to the public, at the latest at the end of each task, and public reports will be made available online once approved by the EC. Before uploading, the data will be checked, cleaned, and validated, including removing outliers and filling in missing information, to ensure data accuracy.

10. Allocation of resources

The costs required to ensure that the data collected or reused during the R-Map activities comply with the FAIR principles are included in the project budget, mainly in the form of effort. This includes costs related to data collection, documentation, storage, access security, preservation and overall data management. Long-term preservation costs are expected to be minimal, as the project's open data will be stored free of charge in reputable repositories.

Specific data management roles will be established to ensure that R-Map data is handled effectively, accurately and securely. All involved partners will sign an agreement outlining their responsibilities and obligations regarding data sharing. This agreement will specify conditions for the protection of personal data, define obligations and assign responsibilities. Each partner is responsible for their own data processing, and access to other partners' data is only allowed if it is completely anonymised.

In general, the PC will have overall responsibility for data management within the R-Map project and will coordinate with the WPL and TL on the collection and storage of all data during the life of the project, as well as what data and how it will be opened up for re-use. In addition, the coordinator is responsible for overseeing the implementation of the project in terms of GDPR at the project level and uploading the data to the Zenodo repository. Each partner is locally responsible for the local collection, anonymisation and secure storage of their data.

11. Other research outputs

No other research outputs have been identified in the first version of the R-Map Data Management Plan, or are expected to be generated or reused as part of the project.

12. Data security

R-Map is committed to the secure management of all data collected, generated, or reused throughout its lifecycle, and emphasizes the importance of protecting this information from accidental loss or unauthorised access. To achieve this, the project will implement appropriate technical and organizational safeguards after a risk assessment of the data involved, considering the potential impact and likelihood of a breach. The project's approach to data security is designed to reduce the risk of a breach, whether caused by human error or hardware problems, during and after the completion of R-Map, and to prevent unauthorised access to the data.

The project partners are all responsible for handling the data securely, using methods such as private servers or cloud service providers that comply with legal data protection regulations such as GDPR. They will ensure that data is protected, with the necessary security measures in place to minimize the risk of data breaches or loss. Partners are also responsible for providing secure storage and backup services for project staff, with regular automated backups recommended. In addition, project participants are encouraged to use password-protected servers within their organizations to store data and materials, and to limit access to authorised individuals.

13. Ethics

The solutions proposed by R-Map do not involve, use or study sensitive personal information for any reason. Therefore, there are no ethical concerns regarding sensitive personal data. The project consortium will comply with the ethical guidelines and principles of the Horizon programme and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union throughout the project. Ethical, social and data privacy factors are of utmost importance and will be carefully considered.

When dealing with **personal data**, the R-Map partners take the following guidelines into account:

- Avoidance of unnecessary collection of personal data.
- Personal data is only collected with the explicit consent of the individual concerned.
- The personal information collected will be treated confidentially and carefully, using appropriate technology to protect the information.
- Any incidental personal data collected during the research will be deleted immediately. However, the ultimate goal is to reduce the amount of this type of ancillary data as much as possible.
- None of the data collected is for sale or use for purposes other than the current project.

All personal data collected or generated (e.g., interviews, surveys, R-Map platform operation) will be processed based on informed consent, in compliance with the GDPR and relevant applicable EU and national regulations. The United Kingdom has an adequacy decision⁵ that allows for the free movement of personal data between the EU and the United Kingdom. In Türkiye, the GDPR does not apply, and there is no adequacy decision between the EU and Türkiye certifying that Türkiye's legal framework for personal data is comparable to the GDPR. Personal data transfers to Türkiye must comply with the Standard Contractual Clauses for International Transfers.⁶ All interview output collected by Türkiye (Koç University) will be anonymized. No personal information will be retained. The collected data will be stored at Koç University's institutional Microsoft OneDrive cloud services. Only authorized personnel will have access to data collected by Koç University.

R-Map is contractually obliged to retain project data for up to five years after the end of the project (unless auditors request further retention). At the end of the retention period, and unless there are further legitimate reasons for retention, partners are required to dispose the personal data securely.

⁵https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/international-dimension-data-protection/adequacy-decisions_en

⁶ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec_impl/2021/914/oj

14. Other issues

No use of other national data management procedures has been identified in this first version. If so, they will be mentioned in the next versions.

15. Conclusion

The current document is the first version of the R-Map Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan. It contains all relevant information about the project management, the quality assurance plan of the project, the types of data and the data management policy of the project, in particular about making the data FAIR.

The R-MAP Management and Quality Plan and Data Management Plan is a living document that will be continually updated to reflect new developments and findings. Further revisions are planned at two specific points in the project timeline - M15 and M36.

ANNEX

CONSENT AFTER INFORMATION

I. INFORMATION SHEET

Study title: [R-Map Mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the effects of remote working arrangements in urban and rural areas — GA 101132497]

Principal Investigator: [name of the partner & organization responsible for implementing survey]

Project Coordinator: Efstratios Stylianidis Professor, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), <sstyl@auth.gr>

Funding Organisation:[European Research Executive Agency (REA), European Commission]

Data Controller: Partner collecting the data

Names of the coordinators of the research/scientific coordinator:

Name : Responsible person for the survey (from the principal investigator organization mentioned above)

Email:

Tel:

Address:

Data Protection Officer (DPO): insert the e-mail address of your organisation

Important Information

You will be given information on the research conducted. [R-Map aims to analyse the impact of remote working arrangements (RWAs) on the disparities between urban and rural regions in Europe]. One of its objectives is to understand current formats and manifestations of remote working arrangements, as well as

their potential socio-economic and spatial effects and their effects on working and living conditions and you will be invited to take part in the study. Your participation is voluntary]. You can talk about this study and the consent form with other people such as family/friends/or whoever you feel comfortable with. You do not have to decide right away. You can decide whether you want to take part in the study after you have thought/discussed this.

There may be words you do not understand or some things you would like for me to explain to you in detail. You can stop anytime and ask questions.

Purpose: Why are we conducting this study?

[Define the purpose of the processing of the data]

[Define that if the data will be further processed, the data subjects will be notified accordingly]

Subject Selection: Why are we requesting your participation?

[You have been invited to take part in this interview/survey/questionnaire xxx because you have been identified as]

[explain why the participation is important]

Your participation is voluntary: Do I have to do this?

You do not have to take part in the study if you don't want to. Even if you say "yes" now, you can change your mind later and pull out of the study at any time.

Participation cost: What will this cost me?

Your participation in the interview does not involve any cost.

Procedure: What will happen if you take part in the study?

[Detailed description of what the participant will do and for how long]

Data: What kind of data will be collected?

[Detailed description of what is going to be recorded/collected and how]

] The interview will be implemented online via zoom or in person based on your preference.

Apart from your views on Remote Working, Your name and e-mail; The organization you belong to;

The information will be collected in the form of written minutes by the interviewer.

The personal data will be handled in accordance with the GDPR and will be stored securely 5 years after the **end of the project** i.e., 31/01/2032.

[The information will be collected in the form of written minutes by the interviewer.

The personal data will be handled in accordance with the GDPR and will be stored securely 5 years after the **end of the project** i.e., 31/01/2032.]

Who will receive or to whom maybe distributed the collected personal data?

[Define whether the data are distributed and to whom]

Personal data is intended **to be transferred/not to be transferred** to a third country or to an international organisation provided that in any case appropriate safeguards are taken.

Clarify that in case that personal data are transferred to third countries that are not subject to the GDPR, due to the potential absence of an adequacy decision and appropriate safeguards, the personal data provided might not be treated according to the principles of the GDPR (EU Regulation 2016/679).

Risks: Is this bad or dangerous for me?

There are no risks involved in this study.

Benefits: Will this be beneficial for me?

[By participating in this interview, you will **be contributing ++++**]

Sharing the results: Will you inform me on the conclusions?

When the research is finished, I will be able to explain to you everything we have learned. An informational brochure will be available upon your request. Later on, we will inform other people about the research we have made and what we have found. This will be accomplished by writing articles and meeting with people that are interested in what we do.

Right to refuse or withdraw: I can choose not to be part of this study? Can I change my mind?

Your participation is not forced. You can stop the research at any time if you wish.

Consent is provided for **[XXXX months/years]** [the time period for which consent is given shall be in consistency with the time period that the personal data will be kept] until it is revoked by sending an e-mail to **[XXXXX]** or by sending the application form enclosed at the end of this document to the address of the coordinator of the research/scientific. The right to withdraw consent at any time does not affect the lawfulness of the processing based on the consent given before its withdrawal.

Data managing

The processing of your personal data is based on consent to this processing for specific purpose. Your personal data will be codified and saved at computers in accordance with appropriate technical and organisational measures. [define in a simple and clear way these technical and organisational measures that will be taken with the view of data protection].

You have the right to request from the Head of the Research access to or rectification or erasure of your personal data or restriction of processing concerning your data or to object to processing as well as the right to data portability. [You can choose which of these rights are feasible to be conferred on]. For any enquiry or guidance regarding your rights, you could send an email to [XXXXX] or phone at [0-XXXXXX]. Any change in your personal data will take place within 30 days of your communication with Principal Investigator.

If you have any questions about your personal data and your relevant rights or if you believe that your rights are being violated, you can contact the **Data Protection Officer xxx**. For additional protection you have the right to lodge a complaint with the Hellenic Data Protection Authority (www.dpa.gr).

If you finally decide that you would like to take part in the study you will receive a copy of this sheet.

II. CONSENT

[RESEARCH NAME]

I the undersigned

I declare that:

- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed by (name and position/area of responsibility of the researcher) for the purposes of the research in which I will participate and which is part of the research project R-Map Mapping, understanding, assessing and predicting the effects of remote working arrangements in urban and rural areas — GA 101132497.
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about the method and sources of the research financing.
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about what my participation in this research entails. In particular, I have been informed of all the rights and obligations I will have as a participant in the research comprising the obligation of confidentiality (if the latter is required).
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about any positive or directly negative, short-term or long-term consequence my participation in this research is expected to have concerning me or in relation with third parties.
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about how my personal data related to this research is processed and protected.
- I am aware of the fact that my participation is voluntary and that I can withdraw my participation from the research at any time for any reason and without any impact on me (as well as of the fact that the same applies to the person I represent).
- I know the Head of the research to whom I can address to withdraw my participation from this research or to notify any potential problem that might arise during my participation or after the completion of this research.
- No pressure was exerted to me and I was given enough time to think and decide.

I consent to participate in the above research.

Participant’s Signature: _____ Date: _____ day/month/year

GA 101132497

Partners

Visit: www.r-map.eu
Contact us: <mailto:info@rmap.eu>
Follow us: R-MAP Project EU